

AFP LAYUP OF CF-LM PAEK FUSELAGE SKIN USING A PULSED XENON FLASHLAMP SYSTEM WITH AN OPTICAL-THERMAL SIMULATION TOOL

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ABSTRACT

Xenon flashlamps have emerged as an alternative heat source to the laser in Automated Fibre Placement (AFP) of thermoplastics. These systems are showing sufficient promise to be selected as the fuselage skin layup solution via the AFP process for the Clean Sky II project FRAMES. A Xenon Flashlamp system, consisting of a flashlamp, reflector and quartz light guide, has been shown to reach the temperatures required to process thermoplastic composites in a similar response time to a laser with reduced safety burden. To determine good pulse parameters for CF-LM PAEK for the FRAMES project, an opto-thermal simulation model has been created based on experimental characterisation.

A full optical ray tracing simulation model of the pulsed xenon flashlamp system is required to determine the distribution of energy exiting the light guide and being absorbed by the CF-LM PAEK tapes. Firstly, the xenon plasma source was characterised using spectral irradiance and goniometric measurements. The spectral irradiance measurements in figure 1 (a) show the expected behaviour for a Xenon source, with the measurements at specific voltage ranges used by the pulsed flashlamp system. Furthermore, the goniometric measurements showed the flashlamp can be approximated as a Lambertian emitter for this application. This characterisation data was used to build a source model for the xenon flashlamp within optical ray tracing software and supplemented with literature and datasheet data to complete the optical flashlamp system simulation.

The next step was to determine the energy levels of the pulses entering and exiting the flashlamp system, this was achieved by measuring the electrical pulse energy entering the flashlamp and the optical energy exiting the system light guide. The electrical energy entering a flashlamp was measured using an oscilloscope, with a plot of this shown in figure 1 (b), and the area under the curve giving the energy value. The energy exiting the system light guide was determined using an integrating sphere, with the area under the graph once again giving the energy value, with some of the results shown in figure 1 (c). Based on the measurements in figure 1 (b) and (c), it is possible to calculate the electrical to optical energy conversion efficiency and control energy levels within the simulation tool. Since the optical aspect of the simulation was well characterised, its irradiance profile was transferred to the thermal simulation as shown in figure 1 (d).

Analysis showed that an additional radiative heating process originates from the quartz light guide, which heats up whilst the system is powered, and the resultant heat to the composite tapes via radiation. It is possible to experimentally measure this effect with thermocouples on the surface of a composite tape and build a 3D finite element simulation of this effect, which produced a similar looking thermal curve. The heat flux within this simulation was captured and transferred to the main thermal simulation as a boundary condition, as shown in figure 1 (d).

A finite element analysis (FEA) technique developed in [1] was used to predict the resultant processing temperature within a transient thermal ANSYS simulation. To provide the simulation with its necessary pre-requisite parameters, the thermal diffusion parameters of the CF-LM PAEK material were measured using the DSC and LFA techniques by an external laboratory. In parallel, AFP layup trials were performed, with thermocouples used to provide actual thermal measurements during

processing. The pulse energies used in the trials, with an example shown in figure 1 (b), were measured and scaled to the measured energy curve with the calculated energy efficiency. This data was used to determine optical energy heat flux boundary condition and was programmed to pulse within the simulation. The IR radiation was also scaled and included in runs of the simulation tool for comparative purposes. This simulation tool, as a result, accurately captures the physics behind the two mechanisms heating the CF-LM PAEK tape, but further thermal measurements of the quartz light guide are required to improve the radiative aspect.

Figure 1: (a) Spectral irradiance measurements of xenon flashlamp used in system, (b) oscilloscope measurement of electrical energy entering the system from a single pulse, (c) integrating sphere measurement of energy exiting the system light guide, and (d) heat flux boundary conditions imported into the transient thermal FE simulation for both optical energy from flashlamp and IR radiation from heating of the light guide.

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REFERENCES

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